

Participation of Administrative Staff in Decision-Making and Their Relation to the Nature of Work in Universities

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Abstract: *The objective of the study is to identify the extent of participation of administrative staff in decision making and their relation to the nature of work in universities. A comparative study between Al-Azhar and Islamic Universities, The researchers used the random stratified sample method in the study. The study was conducted on a sample of (221) administrative staff from Al-Azhar and Islamic Universities. The response rate was (82.35%). The study reached a number of results, the most important of which is that there is a medium degree of participation of decision-making staff in the Palestinian universities in Gaza Strip from the point of view of the administrative staff. The percentage reached (67.76%). There is a high level of satisfaction with the nature of work, where the percentage was (74.96%). There is a direct correlation between the participation of workers in decision-making and the nature of work prevailing. There are differences between the sample according to the gender variable in their perception of the participation of decision makers and the nature of work in favor of female participation in decision-making and in favor of males in the nature of work, the absence of differences in the perception of workers to participate in decision-making and the nature of work depending on the variable age. There are differences of statistical significance in the perception of the participation of workers in decision-making and the nature of work depending on the variable of scientific qualification, that the differences in the participation of decision makers and the nature of work according to the scientific qualification were in favor of those who obtained the diploma degree compared to other practical qualifications, the absence of differences in the perception of workers to participate in decision-making and the nature of work depending on the variable years of service for the years of service (5-7 years), the absence of differences in the perception of employees to participate in decision-making and the nature of work according to the variable level of career (Director, Head of Department, and Administrative Officer), the absence of differences in the perception of workers to participate in decision-making and the nature of work depending on the variable workplace, and the existence of differences in the perception of workers to participate in decision-making and the nature of work depending on the university working for the Islamic University.*

The study reached a number of recommendations, the most important of which is that the managements of the Palestinian universities in the Gaza Strip should be more interested in the participation of decision-makers by delegating authority and using the democratic approach in leadership, continuing the managements of the universities of interest and continuous improvement of the nature of the work of its employees, enhancing the periodic evaluation of job performance and to inform employees and express their opinion, solving employees' problems and giving them the opportunity to contribute to solving their own problems, and the use of the staff rotation method periodically.

Keywords: participation of administrative staff, decision making, nature of work, administrative staff, Palestinian universities, Gaza Strip, Palestine.

1. INTRODUCTION

The effectiveness and efficiency of individual and collective performance and the overall functioning of an organization depend on the extent to which the climate in the internal work environment influences many decisions, behavior and attitudes towards the organization, where the individual's behavior within the organization is influenced by the surrounding environment, and towards and aware of that environment Al-Sakran, 2004).

Universities are a good example of organizations that need the participation of administrative staff in decision-making in order to improve the performance of their employees so that they can carry out their vital function of society. In this sense, the idea of the present study came as the researchers

seek to study the participation of administrative staff in decision-making (Al Shobaki et al., 2018), (El Talla et al., 2017) and (Abu-Naser et al., 2017).

The interest in studying the issue of the participation of administrative staff in decision-making in universities has increased in order to increase the sense of importance and place of workers in determining the future of their universities, as well as the influence they have in developing the reality and objectives of these universities (Al Shobaki et al., 2017), (El Talla et al., 2018) and (Abu-Naser et al., 2016).

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

The identification of the factors that affect the performance of employees in the institution in a positive or

negative is the responsibility of officials in the management of any institution and the neglect of recognition or seek to improve the characteristics of the institution that distinguish them from others is one of the causes of management problems, and through the survey researchers concluded that There is a disparity in the performance of staff in Palestinian universities in the Gaza Strip, and there are many factors that affect their performance, so this study aims to identify the participation of administrative staff in decision-making and their relation to the nature of work in universities, in order to help draw attention Departments of these universities to the importance of improving and addressing the negative aspects of the advancement of these universities and face the obstacles faced by administrative and technical (Al Shobaki et al., 2018), (El Talla et al., 2018) and (Abu-Naser et al., 2017).

The problem of research is to answer the following questions:

Q1- What is the reality of the participation of decision makers in Palestinian universities?

Q2: What is the level of satisfaction of the employees about the nature of work prevailing in Palestinian universities?

Q3: Is there a relationship between the extent of participation of decision makers and the nature of work prevailing in Palestinian universities from the perspective of administrative staff?

3. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

This study aims to achieve the following objectives:

1. Identifying the participation of decision makers in Palestinian universities.
2. Highlighting the nature of work prevailing in Palestinian universities.
3. Analyzing the relationship between the extent of participation of decision makers and the nature of work prevailing in Palestinian universities.
4. Identifying the differences in the employees' perceptions of the extent of participation of decision makers and the nature of work prevailing in Palestinian universities according to the demographic and organizational variables (gender, age, qualifications, years of service, job level, and work place).
5. Providing suggestions and recommendations that help the management of Palestinian universities and all departments working in the field of education to develop the participation of decision makers and improve the nature of work prevailing.

4. RESEARCH IMPORTANCE

The importance of the study is shown by the benefit that will be given to:

1. It may help the management of universities and human resources managers in them to identify the dimensions of the relationship between the extents of the involvement of decision makers with the nature of work in universities.

2. In addition to this vital field of research, it is one of the important areas that dealt with the concept of participation of decision-makers and facing the need of universities of human competencies that help in solving the problems that confront the workers in the nature of their work.
3. It dealt with important topics of organizational behavior, namely, the participation of decision makers and the nature of work, and its vital role in influencing many other variables within the organization related to employees.

5. RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

In order to provide an appropriate answer to the questions posed, and the study seeks to test the validity of the following assumptions:

H01: There is a statistically significant relationship between the participation of workers in decision-making and the nature of work prevailing in Palestinian universities.

H02: There are statistically significant differences between the extent of participation of decision makers and the nature of work prevailing in universities according to demographic and organizational variables (gender, age, qualifications, years of service, job level, and work place).

This hypothesis is divided into several sub-hypotheses as follows:

H02-1: There are statistically significant differences between the extent of participation of decision makers and the nature of work prevailing in universities according to the gender variable.

H02-2: There are statistically significant differences between the extent of participation of decision makers and the nature of work prevailing in universities according to the age variable.

H02-3: There are statistically significant differences between the extent of participation of decision makers and the nature of work prevailing in universities according to the variable of scientific qualification.

H02-4: There are statistically significant differences between the extent of participation of decision makers and the nature of work prevailing in universities according to the variable years of service.

H02-5: There are statistically significant differences between the extent of participation of decision makers and the nature of work prevailing in universities according to the level of employment.

H02-6: There are statistically significant differences between the extent of participation of decision makers and the nature of work prevailing in universities according to the variable of the workplace.

H03: There are differences related statistically between the extent of participation of decision makers and the nature of work prevailing in universities depending on the university in which they work.

6. RESEARCH VARIABLES:

- **Independent variables:** the extent of participation of decision makers.
- **Dependent variable:** nature of work
- **Demographic and organizational variables** (gender, age, academic qualification, years of service, job level, workplace, university).

7. RESEARCH LIMITS AND SCOPE

- **Academic Limit:** Participation of Administrative Staff in Decision-Making and Their Relation to the Nature of Work in Universities Comparative Study between Al - Azhar and Islamic Universities
- **Human Limit:** This study is limited to the responses of administrative staff.
- **Institutional Limit:** The study was conducted on the main universities in the Gaza governorates (Al-Azhar and Islamic).
- **Time Limits:** This study was implemented in 2018 and therefore represents the reality at this time.

8. RESEARCH TERMINOLOGY

- **The extent of participation of decision makers:** Participation in decision making gives employees opportunities to express opinions, ideas and suggestions, which can lead to improved working methods, reduce conflict and raise the morale of individuals and groups, as the decision is the essence of the administrative process and its basic means of achieving the goals of the organization (Hamoud, 2002). Participatory participation in decision-making is the opposite of the individual approach. Participatory approach is characterized by improving the organizational climate, which leads to the sense of importance of individuals; it also makes them more understanding of the circumstances of the decision, and increases their knowledge of the factors affecting decision-making. Implementing the objectives of the resolution (Al-Kutbi, 2005).
- **Nature of work:** The nature of work is an important factor in motivating or discouraging workers. Routine work leads to boredom, neglect, apathy, and indifference to the adoption of modernization or development. The worker often feels that his work is not important. It encourages employees to contribute their full potentials and creative energies to the development of their potentials and potentials for successful work and achievement of goals (Hamoud, 2002).

9. LITERATURE REVIEW

- Study of (Ahmed et al., 2018) aimed to examine the Information Technology used and its effect on the nature of the work of the administrators at Al-Azhar University in Gaza. The researchers used the analytical descriptive method through a questionnaire randomly distributed

among the employees of Al-Azhar University in Gaza. The study was conducted on a sample of 77 employees the response rate was 92.20%. The study reached a number of results, the most important of which is that there is a high degree of Information Technology Used at Al-Azhar University- Gaza from the point of view of the administrative staff, where the percentage (74.14%). And that there is a high level of the prevailing the Nature of Administrators Work from the point of view of administrative staff, where the percentage (72.14%), there is a direct correlation between the Information Technology Used and the Nature of Administrators Work, there is a statistically significant effect of the Information Technology Used on the Nature of Administrators Work at the university, the absence of differences between the sample according to the variable (gender and variable age) in their perception of the Information Technology Used and the Nature of Administrators Work, there are differences of statistical Sig. in the perception depending on the variable of scientific qualification in Field of the Nature of Administrators Work, while there were no differences in Field: technology used, the differences in the Nature of Administrators Work according to the scientific qualification were in favor of those who obtained the diploma degree compared to postgraduate studies, the absence of differences in the perception of employees of the Information Technology Used and the Nature of Administrators Work according to the variable years of service, and the variable level of employment (manager, head of department, administrative officer), and the change of the workplace. The study reached a number of recommendations, the most important of which is the necessity of giving universities the opportunity to participate in decision-making, the continued administration of universities interest and continuous improvement of the performance of its employees, the need to strengthen the periodic evaluation of job performance and to inform the employees and to express their opinion, the importance of solving the problems of Employees and giving them the opportunity to contribute to solving their own problems, the need to use the method of rotation of employees and periodically, and the importance of strengthening the democratic leadership style and empowering university staff.

- Study of (FarajAllah et al., 2018) aimed to know the relationship between the nature of the work and the type of communication among the Employees in the Palestinian universities. A comparative study between Al-Azhar University and Al-Aqsa University. The researchers used the analytical descriptive method through a questionnaire that is randomly distributed among the employees of Al-Azhar and Al-Aqsa universities in Gaza Strip. The study was conducted on a sample of (176) administrative employees from the

surveyed universities. The response rate was (85.79%). The study reached a number of results, the most important of which is that there is a high degree of satisfaction with the nature of work prevailing in the Palestinian universities in Gaza Strip from the point of view of the administrative staff, where the percentage was (68.15%). There is a Mean level of communication from the point of view of administrative staff, with a percentage of (67.50%). There is a direct correlation between the nature of the work and the prevailing pattern of communication. There is an absence of differences between the sample according to the gender variable in their perception of the nature of work and the prevailing pattern of communication. There is an absence of differences in the perception of Employees nature of work and the pattern of communication prevailing depending on the variables (age, years of service, job level, and university). There are statistically significant differences between Al-Azhar University and Al-Aqsa University in favor of Al-Azhar University. The study reached a number of recommendations, the most important of which is that the interest of the management of the Palestinian universities in Gaza Strip in general, and Al-Aqsa and Al-Azhar Universities in particular should be provided with a good nature of work and communication. There is a need for continuing the management of universities to pay attention and continuous improvement of the performance of employees. There is an importance of solving the problems of Employees and giving them the opportunity to contribute to solving their own problems. Staff rotation should be used periodically and the need to strengthen the democratic leadership style and empower university Employees.

- Study of (Madi et al., 2018) aimed to identify The Organizational Structure and its impact on the pattern of leadership in the Palestinian university in Gaza Strip. The researchers used the analytical descriptive method through a questionnaire randomly distributed among Palestinian university Employees in Gaza Strip. The study was conducted on a sample of (320) administrative staff from the three universities. The required sample calculated according to the law (274) Employees, and the response rate was (81.87%). The study found that there is a high degree of satisfaction with the nature of The Organizational Structure in the Palestinian universities in Gaza Strip from the point of view of the administrative staff, which reached (68.05%). The results showed that there was a Mean level of participation of decision-makers, with a percentage of (64.91%). There is a direct correlation between the nature of The Organizational Structure and the participation of decision makers. There is a significant impact of The Organizational Structure on the participation of decision makers. There is absence of differences between the sample according to the gender

variable in their perception of the nature of The Organizational Structure and the extent of participation of decision-makers. There is absence of differences in the perception of Employees to the nature of The Organizational Structure and the participation of decision-making Employees depending on the age variable. There are statistically Sig. differences according to the variable of scientific qualification in The Organizational Structure, while there were no differences in the extent of participation of decision-making personnel. And the absence of differences in the perception of the Employees of the nature of The Organizational Structure and the participation of decision-making staff according to the variable years of service, the variable level of employment (manager, head of department, administrative officer), the variable of the workplace, and there are differences in the perception of the Employees of the nature of The Organizational Structure and the participation of decision-making personnel depending on the university in which they work in all areas. And that there are significant differences between the Islamic University and Al-Azhar University in The Organizational Structure, the extent of the participation of decision-making personnel, in favor of the Islamic University. And that there are statistically significant differences between Al-Azhar University and Al-Aqsa University in the extent of the participation of decision makers in favor of Al-Azhar University. The study reached a number of recommendations, the most important of which is that the management of the Palestinian universities in Gaza Strip in general, and the Al-Aqsa and Al-Azhar Universities should be particularly interested in providing an appropriate and flexible The Organizational Structure. There is a need for the universities to have the opportunity for Employees to participate in decision-making, the importance of continuing the managements of the universities interest and continuous improvement of the performance of its Employees, the need to solve the problems of Employees and give them the opportunity to contribute to solve their own problems, the use of the staff rotation method periodically, and strengthening the democratic leadership style and empowering university staff.

- Study of (Almasri et al., 2018) aimed to study The Organizational Structure and its role in applying the Information Technology Used the Palestinian universities as a comparative study between Al-Azhar and Islamic universities. The researchers used the analytical descriptive method through a questionnaire that randomly distributed among Palestinian university workers in Gaza Strip. A sample of (182) administrative staff from the two universities, the response rate was (81.35%). The study reached a number of results, the most important of which is that there is a high level of the Information Technology Used from the perspective

of administrative staff, there is a direct correlation between The Organizational Structure and the Information Technology Used, the role and impact of The Organizational Structure in the nature of the Information Technology Used, the absence of differences between the sample according to the variable (gender and age), there are statistically significant differences in the perception of The Organizational Structure and the Information Technology Used according to the variable of scientific qualification in The Organizational Structure, while there were no differences in Field of the Information Technology Used, the differences in The Organizational Structure according to the scientific qualification were in favor of those who obtained the diploma degree compared to other practical qualifications, the absence of differences in the perception of employees The Organizational Structure and the Information Technology Used depending on the variable years of service, the differences in The Organizational Structure and technology perception depending on the job level variable (Director, Head of Section, and Administrative Officer) for the benefit of the Administrative Officer, the absence of differences in the perception of employees The Organizational Structure and the Information Technology Used depending on the workplace variable, the differences in the perception of employees The Organizational Structure and the Information Technology Used by the University working for the Islamic University. The study reached a number of recommendations, the most important of which is that the managements of the Palestinian universities in Gaza Strip should be given more attention to the existing The Organizational Structure and modified to suit the need of work, the need for universities to continue to pay attention to the continuous improvement of the Information Technology Used and strengthening the democratic leadership style and empowering university staff.

- Study of (Abu Sultan et al., 2018) aimed to identify the type of leadership and its role in determining the type of administrative communication at the Islamic University. The researchers used the method of Stratified random sampling in the study. The study was conducted on a sample of 144 administrative staff from the Islamic University of Gaza. The response rate was 77.08%. The study found that there is a high degree of satisfaction with The Style of Leadership in the Islamic University - Gaza from the point of view of the administrative staff, where the percentage reached (73.52%). There is a high degree of satisfaction with the pattern of communication prevailing in the Islamic University - Gaza from the point of view of administrative staff, where the percentage (76.52%). There is a direct correlation between The Style of Leadership and communication pattern, the role of The Style of Leadership in

determining the type of administrative communication at the Islamic University- Gaza. There are no differences in the perception of workers in the pattern of communication while there are differences in The Style of Leadership according to the age variable in favor of the lower age groups. There are no statistically significant differences in the perception of the leadership pattern according to the variable (gender, qualification) and the absence of differences in the perception of the employees of The Style of Leadership and style of communication depending on the variable years of service, and the absence of differences in the perception of the employees of The Style of Leadership and style of communication depending on the level of career variable (manager, head of department, administrative officer). The study reached a number of recommendations, the most important of which is that the interest of the departments of the Palestinian universities and the Islamic University should be increased in order to provide and maintain a good The Style of Leadership, the need to improve the existing communication pattern at the university and to give universities the opportunity to participate in decision-making, the importance of solving the problems of workers and giving them the opportunity to contribute to solving their own problems. The need to use the method of rotation of employees and periodically, and the importance of promoting democratic leadership and empowerment of university staff.

- Study of (Al Shobaki et al., 2018) aimed to identify the performance of the administrative staff in the Palestinian universities in Gaza Strip. The researchers used the analytical descriptive method through a questionnaire distributed randomly to the sample of 320 administrative staff from the three universities. The response rate was (81.87%). The study reached a number of results, the most important of which is that there is a high level of performance from the point of view of the administrative staff, as the percentage reached (81.51%). The results showed that there were no differences in the perception of the employees according to the variables "age, years of service, job level (manager, head of department, administrative officer), place of work". The results showed that there are differences in the perception of employees to perform the function depending on the university variable, where the results indicated that there are statistically significant differences between the Islamic University and Al-Aqsa University in the job performance in favor of the Islamic University. The study reached a number of recommendations, the most important of which is that the managements of the three Palestinian universities in Gaza Strip should give special attention to job performance in general and Al-Aqsa University and Al-Azhar University in particular. The Employees of universities should have the opportunity to participate in

decision-making. The Management of the three universities should keep interest in continuous improvement of the performance of their employees. Enhancing the periodic evaluation of the job performance, informing employees about their evaluations, and giving them the chance to express their opinion about it. Solving employees' problems and giving them the opportunity to contribute in solving their own problems. And the use of the staff rotation method periodically.

- Study of (El Talla et al., 2017) aimed to investigate the relationship between the organizational variables and job performance at Gaza strip Universities, the organizational variables included: communication style, nature of work, the technology used. And it aimed to identify the extent of differences statistically significant in employees trends toward the reality of organizational variables attributed to some characteristics of the study population. The data has been collecting using a questionnaire consisting of (50) paragraphs. The questionnaire was distributed randomly to (320) employees of the administrative staff in Gaza strip universities; (262) employees responded, and the results showed the availability of a high degree of organizational variables in Gaza Universities, the order of variables were as follows: the technology used, the nature of work, and finally communication style, and it showed a high level of job performance, in addition the results showed a significant correlation between organizational variables and job performance, and there was existence of differences in the perception of the organizational variables depending on the university, for the benefit of the Islamic university, and differences between AlAzhar University and Alaqsa University for the benefit of Al-Azhar University, as results showed no differences between the sample depending on the variables: the functional level and the workplace .
Keywords: organizational variables, communication style, nature of work, used technology, job performance.
- Study of (El Talla, 2015) aimed to investigate the reality of the burnout among Gaza electricity distribution company employees, which included burnout dimensions: Emotional exhaustion, Depersonalization, and Personal accomplishment. And aimed to the organizational causes of burnout, and it aimed to identify the extent of differences statistically significant trends in working toward the reality of burnout attributed to some demographic and organizational characteristics of the study population. The data has been collecting using a Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI) consisting of (22) items. And the questionnaire of organizational causes of burnout consisting of (31) items. The questionnaires were distributed randomly to (69) worker, the results showed that the availability of a medium degree of burnout in the company, and that there is high availability of Emotional exhaustion scope,

average degree for Depersonalization scope and low degree of Personal accomplishment scope. Also the results showed the existence of organizational causes for burnout among employees with the exception of the area of social relations, which was moderately and was the order of the causes are as follows (the weakness of physical stimulation, the limited powers of the work, work stress, conflict of values, poor social relationships). The results showed no differences between the samples due to the variables of gender, age, years of service in their perception of burnout. The researcher recommended the company to work on treatment the causes of burnout, and increase the attention to employees.

- Study of (El Talla, 2014) aimed to investigate the reality of the organizational climate for administrator's staff at Al-Azhar University - Gaza, which included some elements of the organizational climate such as: organizational structure, leadership style and the extent of participation of employees in decision-making. it aimed to identify the extent of differences statistically significant trends in working toward the reality of organizational climate attributed to some demographic and organizational characteristics of the study population. The data has been collecting using a questionnaire. The questionnaire was distributed at random-layer sample to (77) male and female employees of the administrative staff in the university; The results showed that the availability of a medium degree of organizational climate at the Al-Azhar University with percentage (66.64 %), and that there is availability of the average for all scopes of organizational climate, with the exception of leadership style which its degree was high. The orders of scopes were as the following: leadership style , the organizational structure , and finally the extent of participation of employees in decision-making The results showed no differences between the samples due to the variables of gender, age, years of service in their perception of organizational climate, while there are significant differences in the perception of the reality of organizational climate depending on the variable qualification in the areas of (organizational structure, the extent of participation in decision-making and in the total scope of organizational climate); and that differences were in favor of holding a diploma, the differences did not exist in the scope leadership style .
- Study of (Al-Louzi and Zahrani, 2012) aimed at identifying the factors affecting the performance of employees in the Emirate of Baha and determining the most influential in the performance of the job, as well as determining the impact of the difference of these factors according to the demographic factors of the employees (age, type of employment,). Using the comprehensive survey method. The study found a significant correlation between the independent variables combined (work

environment, job communication, incentives, training, management leadership) and job performance, as well as the existence of a positive relation between a factor on one hand and job performance. The results also showed significant differences the results did not show significant differences in the effect of organizational factors on job performance due to social status and age. The study recommended the need to provide a working environment with standard specifications, and to activate the organizational communication, and the diversification of programs of incentives material and moral, because of their impact on the performance of the job.

- A study (Jassim and Hammoud, 2011) aimed at discovering the relationship between the elements of the organizational climate and the management of the university performance through the development of a number of main hypotheses, which states that there is a relationship of significant effect for all elements of the organizational climate in the management of university performance. A sample of (50) faculty members at the University of Muthanna. The study found that there is a relationship between the organizational climate and the management of the university performance, where it was found that there is a relationship of the effect of the elements of the organizational climate in the management of the university performance except the variable participation in decision-making. While the change in leadership style has the highest level of agreement. The study recommended that the university administration take care of the organizational climate by paying attention to its available elements and not available in the work environment in order to improve performance.
- Study of (Bahr and Abu Swirih, 2010) The aim of the study was to identify the extent of statistical differences in the attitudes of employees towards the effect of the elements of the organizational climate on the functional performance due to the demographic characteristics of the members of the study society. The study was conducted using a questionnaire consisting of (80) items, which were distributed randomly to (215) employees and administrative staff of the university, and it was possible to collect (180) valid questionnaires for analysis. The study found that there is a positive organizational climate in the Islamic University and a strong positive relationship between the availability of a good organizational environment and the level of job performance of the Islamic University employees. There is a very good level of job performance for the employees of the Islamic University and the absence of statistically significant differences in the opinions of the sample members on the degree of influence of the elements of the organizational climate on the performance of the administrative staff due to gender, age, academic qualification and place of work.

- Study of (Al-Batoush, 2007) The aim of this course is to understand the impact of the organizational climate on the performance of employees in the Jordan Free Zones Corporation, the relation of the organizational climate, and the performance of the employees with some personal characteristics and career characteristics. The study found a number of results, the most important of which were: The incentives were the first place in terms of the dimensions of the other organizational climate in the Jordan Free Zones Corporation, while the organizational structure was the lowest level, and the managers of the Free Zones Authority did not delegate the powers at the required level. Decisions made at the Jordan Free Zones Corporation are not always made by qualified persons who are related to the subject matter of the decision. The degree of consistency of the organizational structure with the nature of the work and functions of the Jordan Free Zones Corporation is unsatisfactory, (Organizational structure, communication, human resource development) and the performance of employees in the Free Zones Corporation. There is no statistically significant effect between the organizational climate (work systems and procedures, decision making, incentives) and the performance of employees in the Free Zones Corporation, and showed the existence of differences of statistical significance in the organizational climate attributed to the job title, and for the benefit of managers and heads of departments. While there are no differences due to personal and functional characteristics (age, academic qualification, specialization, number of years of service). There were also statistically significant differences in the performance of the employees due to the job title and the benefit of the managers. While there are no differences due to personal and functional characteristics (age, academic qualification, specialization, number of years of service in the institution).
- Study of (Al-Shanti, 2006) Which aimed to identify the extent of the impact of the organizational climate dimensions prevailing in the ministries of the Palestinian National Authority on the performance of human resources, and the assessment of the organizational climate in these ministries as well as to identify the level of performance of human resources. The results of the study were the most important: the attitudes of the sample towards the prevailing organizational climate positive trends, the positive impact of the organizational climate prevailing in the Palestinian ministries on the performance of human resources and that this climate leads to improved performance. It also showed that there is a defect in the organizational structure of the ministries and the methods and methods of decision-making and the disproportionate nature, functions and duties of the jobs occupied by the employees with the scientific qualifications and disciplines obtained.

➤ Study of (Al-Sakran, 2004) the aim of this study was to identify the attitudes of the security sector towards the prevailing organizational climate in this sector and the relation to their performance. One of the most important findings of this study was the high positive attitudes of SS officers towards work systems and procedures. The presence of positive trends high among the officers of the security forces towards administrative communication as one of the axes of the organizational climate affecting the improvement of the performance of the job. 3 - The existence of positive trends high among private security officers towards the axis of "employee perception of his role" as one of the axes of performance. The study recommended the following: The need for the attention of officials in the private security forces sector to the components and elements of the organizational climate. And to ensure the development and rehabilitation of the intellectual capacity of all employees in the private security forces. The motivation of the employees of the private security forces sector by supporting them with more material and moral incentives.

10. RELATED WORK

First- Participation of decision makers:

Attention to the policy of decision making is a vital aspect in the formation of the organizational climate for its importance in the development of organizations and ensures continuity of success, and develops the motivation of individuals to practice creative behaviors to enhance the Organization's ability to compete and keep abreast of developments. Hence the opportunity to participate in decision-making raises the interest of employees and motivates them to improve Performance and productivity increase (Al-Adli, 1997).

The interest in decision-making policy is a vital aspect of organizational structure, because it is important for the development of organizations and for ensuring the continuity of their success, and to develop the motivation of individuals to practice innovative behaviors to enhance the organization's ability to keep abreast of developments. The situation is different if the growth is in cases of dominance or centralization leading to the formation of an unhealthy regulatory range, and different forms (Al-Sakran, 2004).

To increase the participation of decision makers, they must be involved in the design of business improvement strategies through Jad Al-rab (2012):

- Improve recruitment, training and performance strategies.
- Use the problem-solving method to enhance individual and community performance improvement skills.
- Identify important processes that need to be redesigned.
- Use new ways to think, innovate and improve quality.

Second- nature of work:

Routine work leads to boredom, neglect, indifference and indifference towards modernization and development;

because creativity is discouraged and the individual feels that his work is not important (Al-Emian, 2005).

The nature of the work greatly affects the performance. The more the nature of work encourages innovation and creativity, the better the performance, the greater the efficiency and the efficiency of the employees and the more the nature of work is routine, the more frustrated the workers.

Therefore, organizations should constantly work on the nature of work commensurate with the qualifications and abilities of the people who are based on it, by putting the right person in the right place, in addition to the periodic rotation of employees in different jobs to kill the spirit of monotony at work, and increase their experience and improve their performance, And to inform them of the importance of the functions and roles they play, and the extent to which this function contributes to the overall productivity of the Organization.

Third- The Palestinian universities under study

The march of the Palestinian universities in the Gaza Strip began with the opening of the Islamic University, which emerged in 1978 from the Azhar Religious Institute and then Al-Azhar University, which in turn emerged from the same institute in 1991. The staff of the Islamic University, Al-Azhar, will be the focus of our study. 466 employees, while at Al-Azhar University (227) employees. The administrative staff in Palestinian universities is an essential component of the organizational structure of Palestinian universities. Without these workers, universities cannot fulfill their great mission of serving the community through their teaching services, research and continuing education. This work is not completed without administrative staff; they carry out various functions in these universities such as student affairs, admission and registration, finance, public relations, personnel affairs, maintenance, procurement, warehousing, services, security and other administrative functions. A must be the availability of a good regulatory environment that helps them to that performance.

In the previous review of the Palestinian universities in the Gaza Strip, the Palestinian universities experienced difficult circumstances in the context of the Israeli occupation, the high demand for Palestinian students to join these universities and the necessary resources, in addition to the lack of material resources necessary to carry out their activities as required, And their dependence mainly on funding fees collected from students, all of which necessitated universities to improve their performance, and since administrative staff are a significant part of the staff of these universities, and they are responsible for the provision of administrative services, (B) of the universities to provide them enhance their affiliation and loyalty to these universities to paper them better and achieve Her message which it was created.

11. ANALYTICAL APPROACH

First- Methodology of the study:

This study deals with the study of tools, phenomena and practices existing and available for study and measurement as they are, without the intervention of researchers in their course, and researchers can interact with them and describe them and analyze them scientifically and objectively the study will rely on two basic types of data:

1. Initial Data:

The study was carried out in the field by distributing questionnaires to study the vocabulary of the study and to collect and compile the necessary information in the subject of the study, and then unloading and analyzing it using the statistical program and using the appropriate statistical SPSS tests in order to arrive at indications of value and indicators that support the subject of the study.

2. Secondary data:

Through the review of books and periodicals, special publications and scientific and professional journals related to the subject of the study, and any references contribute to enrich the study in a scientific way, and the researchers

through the use of secondary sources in the study to identify the foundations and methods of scientific studies in writing studies, Recent developments have occurred in the field of study.

Second: Study Population:

The study population consists of all administrative staff in the main Palestinian universities in the Gaza Strip. These universities are: Islamic University, Al-Azhar University, and through the census of the study society it was found to consist of (655) administrative staff.

Third- The study sample:

- A. A survey sample was used by the researchers to verify the validity and reliability of these tools. The sample size was 32 administrative staff.
- B. The sample was composed of (221) administrative staff from Al-Azhar and Islamic universities. The response rate was (82.35%). The sample distribution and response rate were as in the following table:

Table 1: Number of sample members in each university and the number of respondents

Item	Islamic University	Al-Azhar University	Total
The size of society	428	227	655
The ratio	%65	%35	100%
Distributed sample	144	77	221
Number of respondents	111	71	182
Response rate	77.08%	92.20%	82.35%

Table 2: The distribution of respondents according to university variables, level of employment, gender, age, academic qualification, years of service, place of work

University Name	Islamic University	Al-Azhar University			Total
	111	71			182
Career Level	Director	Head Of The Department	Administrative Employee		
	22	37	123	182	
Gender	Male	Female			182
	131	51			
Age	20-30 years	31-40 years	41-50 years	Greater than 50 years	182
	61	57	42	22	
Qualification	Diploma	BA	Postgraduate		
	55	95	32	182	
Years of service	Less than 5 years	5-7 years	8-10 years	More than 10 years	182
	39	36	15	92	
Workplace	Deanships And Colleges	Financial Services	Administrative Roundabout	Technical Circles	182
	53	21	96	12	

Fourthly- Study tool:

Since the nature of the hypotheses and the variables included in them are the ones that control the choice of the appropriate tool, accordingly, the researchers have prepared a measure of that study commensurate with its objectives and mandates, which measures the extent of participation of decision-makers in relation to the nature of work in universities.

The process of designing and preparing the study scale has gone through several stages and steps:

- 1- See literature and previous studies related to the subject of the present study.
- 2- Collect and define scale paragraphs.
- 3- Formulation of the standard expressions according to the study sample.

- 4- Set the meter instructions.
- 5- How to correct the meter.
- 6- Conduct a study of stability and honesty of the scale.

Scale units:

The final scale included 20 words distributed across the two variables.

How to correct the meter:

The five-dimensional Likert scale was used to measure respondents' responses to the questionnaire sections according to the following table:

Table 3: Questionnaire Answering Model

Response	Strongly Disagree	disagree	neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Degree	1	2	3	4	5

Each question has five answers (strongly disagree - disagree - neutral – agree - strongly agree), asking the respondent to read each question or answer with an ✓ sign in proportion to his or her vision of reality, (Strongly Agree) Five points, (agree) four points, (neutral) three points, (disagree) two points, and (strongly disagree) one point, so that the relative weight in the last case is 20% and is proportional to this response.

Believe the meter: The researchers calculated the validity of the meter in the following ways:

1. **Authentic honesty:** Researchers have verified the authenticity of the tool ostensibly by presenting to a group of holders of a doctorate degree in business administration, and the apparent honesty shows the general appearance of the test in terms of relevance to the examinees, and the affiliation of the phrase to the field, and clarity of wording and instructions.

2. **Authenticity of internal consistency:** The internal consistency coefficient is a correlation coefficient between each unit of scale and the whole scale, so this method is usually used to determine the veracity of the test on the one hand and the viability of its units on the other. The researchers calculated the validity of the internal consistency of the scale by finding the correlation coefficients between each field and the total score of the scale. The researchers conducted a survey sample of 32 Employees by finding correlation coefficients for each paragraph in the field to which they belong, as well as correlation coefficients between each field And the scale as a whole, as in the following tables:

Table 4: Honesty coefficients for each paragraph with the total score of the scope of participation of decision-making personnel

No.	Item	Honesty level	Level of Sig.
1.	Employees participate in setting goals for departments and departments.	0.771	0.01
2.	Decision-makers resort to consultations before making decisions to determine their results and effects	0.811	0.01
3.	Employees have the power and authority to make decisions about their work and take responsibility	0.533	0.01
4.	Management philosophy allows employees to solve their own problems	0.610	0.01
5.	Management is keen to involve subordinates in decision-making	0.713	0.01
6.	The problems facing the departments and divisions are solved collectively	0.470	0.01
7.	Different alternatives are evaluated and available before decisions are made	0.738	0.01
8.	The level of cooperation between colleagues is appropriate	0.367	0.05
9.	Employees are involved in developing performance standards related to their functions	0.714	0.01
10.	Employees participate in the process of evaluating their performance	0.694	0.01

Table 5: Honesty coefficients for each paragraph with the total degree of field of nature of work

No.	Item	Honesty level	Level of Sig.
1.	Working hours and working days are appropriate	0.563	0.01
2.	Office designs provide psychological and physical comfort (ventilation, lighting, movement)	0.381	0.05
3.	Management provides security and safety features	0.366	0.05
4.	Me work gives me many opportunities for innovation	0.604	0.01
5.	The size of the work is consistent with my personal abilities and my	0.640	0.01

No.	Item	Honesty level	Level of Sig.
	scientific qualifications		
6.	My work requirements are consistent with my abilities and skills	0.692	0.01
7.	I am satisfied with the duties and tasks at work	0.591	0.01
8.	My job gives me appreciation and respect for others in society	0.715	0.01
9.	University employees enjoy the holidays they are entitled to according to the system	0.535	0.01
10.	My job provides stability and job security	0.457	0.01

It is clear from the previous table that all coefficients of honesty are high and all function at level (0.05). This gives confidence in the ability of the measure to discriminate.

Stability of the scale:

The concept of stability means the ability of the test to give the same grades or values to the same individual or individuals if the measurement process is repeated. To

Table 6: Coefficient of stability of the scale of participation of administrative staff in decision-making and its relation to the nature of work in universities

No.	Field	No. of Items	Correlation Coefficient Before Adjustment	Correlation Coefficient After Adjustment	Level of Sig.
1.	The extent of participation of decision makers	10	0.648	0.787	Sig. at 0.01
2.	the Nature of Work	10	0.565	0.722	Sig. at 0.01

From the above table, we can see that the stability coefficients in all midterm segments were high, indicating that the questionnaire has a high degree of stability.

2- Cronbach’s Coefficient Alpha stability of persistence: The researchers used the α -cronbach

Table 7: Shows the coefficients of Cronbach’s Coefficient Alpha stability each dimension of the scale

No.	Field	Cronbach’s Coefficient Alpha stability
1.	The extent of participation of decision makers	0.853
2.	the Nature of Work	0.731

The above table shows that all Cronbach’s Coefficient Alpha stability are above (0.731). This indicates that the questionnaire has a high degree of stability.

Fifth- Statistical Methods:

The computer was used in the statistical processing, especially the statistical packages program (SPSS), where all the data obtained by the researchers and then the results were extracted through the scientific equations necessary for this and the most important used in this study:

1. Averages, frequencies, standard deviations and percentages.
2. Spearman Brown’s correlation coefficient for the equal half - division, and the Cronbach alpha factor to determine the stability of the resolution.

Table 8: Scale of measurements used in this study

The Level Method	Very Low	Low	Medium	High	Very High
SMA	Less than (1.80)	From (1.80): (2.59)	From (2.60): (3.39)	From (3.40):(4.19)	Greater than (4.20)
Relative Weight	Less than 36.00%	From 36.00: 51.90%	From 52.00: 67.90%	From 68.00: 83.90%	Greater than 84.00%

ensure the stability of the scale, the researchers used the following methods:

- 1- **Method of split half:** by calculating the correlation coefficient between the individual questions and marital questions, and obtained the stability coefficients shown in the following table.

coefficient to calculate the stability coefficient for all the parameters of the standard, which is a high stability coefficient indicating the strength and validity of the scale.

3. Pearson correlation coefficient to measure the relationship between variables.
4. T test to find the differences between the averages.
5. Analysis of mono-variance to see differences between more than two groups.
6. Scheffe post-test to measure the direction of differences.

Answer the study questions:

Q1-: What is the reality of the participation of decision makers in Palestinian universities?

To answer the study questions and to use the pentagram in the study instrument, the study adopted the criterion mentioned by Abdul Fattah (2008) to judge the trend when using the pentagram. The following table illustrates this:

This indicates that the Means of less than 1.80 indicate a very low degree in the elements of Field. The Means of (1.80: 2.59) indicate a low degree of availability of field elements, (2.60: 3.39) indicate that there is a medium degree in the elements of Field, and the Means ranging from (3.40: 4.19) indicate that there is a large degree in the elements of Field. More than (4.20) indicate that there is a very large

degree in the elements of Field on the scale used in the study shown in the previous table.

To answer this question, the researchers resorted to repetitions, averages, standard deviation, percentages and order. The results were as shown in the following table:

Table 9: Frequency, Mean, Standard Deviation, Percentages and Ranking of Responses of Sample Members in the Scope of Participation of Decision-Making Workers

No.	Item	Total Scores	Mean (5)	Standard Deviation	Percentage	Rank
1.	Employees participate in setting goals for departments and departments.	626	3.44	1.000	68.80%	3
2.	Decision-makers resort to consultations before making decisions to determine their results and effects	614	3.37	0.894	67.40%	8
3.	Employees have the power and authority to make decisions about their work and take responsibility	632	3.47	0.884	69.40%	2
4.	Management philosophy allows employees to solve their own problems	606	3.39	0.875	67.80%	7
5.	Management is keen to involve subordinates in decision-making	578	3.18	0.993	63.60%	9
6.	The problems facing the departments and divisions are solved collectively	620	3.41	0.980	68.20%	6
7.	Different alternatives are evaluated and available before decisions are made	608	3.42	0.924	68.40%	4
8.	The level of cooperation between colleagues is appropriate	688	3.80	0.885	76.00%	1
9.	Employees are involved in developing performance standards related to their functions	619	3.42	0.949	68.40%	5
10.	Employees participate in the process of evaluating their performance	540	2.97	1.092	59.40%	10
All items of the dimension		616.65	3.3882	.646630	67.76%	

The above table shows the results achieved in the field of participation of decision-makers by presenting the mathematical averages of the fields. The averages were between 2.97 and 3.80.

We note from the previous table that all the paragraphs range from medium to high. There are six paragraphs in this field with a high percentage between 68% and 83.90%. Four paragraphs have a medium score between (52.00%) and (76.90%). The paragraph (level of growth among suitable colleagues) was estimated at ratio of (76.00%) followed by the paragraph (workers have the capacity and legal authority to make decisions about their work and take responsibility) ranked second with 69.40%, the paragraph (Workers involved in setting goals of departments and divisions) ranked third with a percentage (68.80%). The percentage of those who participated in the evaluation of their performance ranked in last place with a percentage (59.40%), and got the total score of the field on a percentage (67.76%), a medium degree.

As a result, there are some positive aspects in the participation of decision-makers such as cooperation between colleagues and the participation of workers in the

development of their work standards. However, there is a shortage in this area, especially in the participation of workers in evaluating their performance. The staff assessment process is still used and does not inform employees of the results of their evaluation or discussion, which requires university administrations to address these problems, to identify shortcomings in the participation of the employees in the decision-making process and to try to address this deficiency.

This finding is consistent with the study of Bahr and Abu Swirih (2010), which showed a relative weight of 65.46%. This indicates that there is an average level of cooperation among colleagues, and that the employees participate to a certain extent in setting the objectives of the work units and decision- This finding was also agreed with Al-Sakran (2004), which showed positive approval for the participation of decision makers. The researchers attributed the reason for this result to the scientific level and service of the sample. This result was opposed with Al-Shanti (2006) , which showed a negative trend among respondents in the PNA ministries on the extent of participation The findings differ from the findings of the study (Jassim and Hammoud, 2011)

and the study (Al-Batoush, 2007) Where there was a weakness in the participation of workers in the decision-making process.

Q2: What is the level of satisfaction of the employees about the nature of work prevailing in Palestinian universities?

Table 10: Frequency, Mean, Standard Deviation, Percentages and Ranking of Responses of Sample Members in the Field of Nature of Work

No.	Item	Total Scores	Mean (5)	Standard Deviation	Percentage	Rank
1.	Working hours and working days are appropriate	688	3.82	0.940	76.40%	6
2.	Office designs provide psychological and physical comfort (ventilation, lighting, movement)	597	3.35	1.156	67.00%	10
3.	Management provides security and safety features	644	3.60	0.915	72.00%	8
4.	My work gives me many opportunities for innovation	648	3.58	0.931	71.60%	9
5.	The size of the work is consistent with my personal abilities and my scientific qualifications	656	3.64	1.006	72.80%	7
6.	My work requirements are consistent with my abilities and skills	701	3.89	0.925	77.80%	3
7.	I am satisfied with the duties and tasks at work	689	3.83	0.908	76.60%	5
8.	My job gives me appreciation and respect for others in society	713	4.03	0.815	80.60%	1
9.	University employees enjoy the holidays they are entitled to according to the system	703	3.91	0.914	78.20%	2
10.	My job provides stability and job security	700	3.89	0.927	77.80%	4
All items of the dimension		682.16	3.7481	.619440	74.96%	

The above table shows the results reached in the field of the nature of work by presenting the arithmetic averages of the fields of the field. It is noted that the averages ranged from (3.35, 4.03).

Table (11) shows that all the paragraphs range from medium to high. There are nine paragraphs in this field that have a high percentage between 68% and 83.90%. One paragraph was also awarded a middle grade between (52.00%) and (67.90%). The paragraph (I have the honor of respecting and respecting others in the community) received the highest percentage (80.60%) followed by the paragraph (university employees enjoy the leaves they deserve according to the system) ranked second with a percentage (78.20%), and the paragraph (my work requirements match my abilities and skills) ranked third with a percentage (77.80%). The paragraph (Ventilation, lighting, movement) was ranked last with (67.00%), and the overall score for the field was 74.96% which is high.

The results can be explained by the fact that the position at the university is one of the most respected jobs in the society. It gives the employee a respectable position. The jobs that the university attracts are according to the description and the job specifications. In addition, the universities grant administrative staff annual leave of 35 days per year and that the work is five days a week, all of these reasons make their satisfaction by the staff on the nature of their work.

Table 11: A correlation matrix between the participation of decision makers and the nature of work in universities

Field	The Nature Of Work
The extent of participation of decision makers	**0.642

This result is consistent with the study of Bahr and Abu Swirih (2010), where the nature of the work at the university gives its employees respect and appreciation in the community and the size of the work corresponds to personal abilities and scientific qualifications and provides stability and job security for workers. The results also agreed with Al-Sakran (2004), which showed a positive attitude towards the nature of work. The researchers attribute this agreement to the general atmosphere of these institutions, the appropriate work environment, and the excellent job performance of employees. (Al-Shanti, 2006), where the results of his study showed that the nature of the work and the duties of the jobs occupied by the workers with the qualifications and disciplines obtained by them, and the researchers explain this result that there is a defect in the organizational structure in the ministries of the Palestinian National Authority.

12. HYPOTHESIS TESTING

H01: There is a statistically significant relationship between the participation of workers in decision-making and the nature of work prevailing in Palestinian universities.

To ascertain the validity of the main hypothesis, the researchers sought to find Pearson correlation coefficient between the participation of decision makers and the nature of work. The results are as shown in the following table:

** Sig. at 0.01

Note from the previous table that there is a positive correlative relationship between the participation of workers in decision-making and the nature of work and this indicates the validity of the main hypothesis of the study.

H02: There are statistically significant differences between the extent of participation of decision makers and the nature of work prevailing in universities according to demographic and organizational variables (gender, age, qualifications, and years of service, job level, and work place).

Table 12: Mean and Standard Deviations and Value of "T" for the Fields of Participation of Administrative Staff in Decision Making and Their Relationship to the Nature of Work according to the Gender Variable

Field	Gender	The Number	Mean	Standard Deviation	"T" value	Level of Sig.
The extent of participation of decision makers	Male	131	3.3275	0.68900	-2.049	0.042
	Female	51	3.5442	0.49484		
the Nature of Work	Male	131	3.8080	0.67000	2.109	0.036
	Female	51	3.5943	.434040		

It is clear from the previous table that there are statistically significant differences due to the gender variable between males and females in all fields, where the value of "T" is calculated higher than the tabular value of T. There are differences between males and females in the extent of participation of decision- Females, which means that females are more satisfied with their participation in decision-making, while in the field of nature of work we find that the differences in favor of males, which means that males are more satisfied with the nature of their work of females, and this proves the validity of the hypothesis.

Table 13: The source of the variance, the sum of squares, the degrees of freedom, the mean squares, the value of "P", and the level of significance attributed to the variable of age

Field	Source	Total Squares	Degrees of Freedom	Average Squares	P Value	Sig.
The extent of participation of decision makers	Between Groups	0.600	3	0.200	0.474	0.701
	Within Groups	75.082	178	0.422		
	Total	75.682	181			
the Nature of Work	Between Groups	2.959	3	0.986	2.641	0.501
	Within Groups	66.492	178	0.374		
	Total	69.451	181			

It is clear from the previous table that there are no statistically significant differences in these fields and the overall score is due to the age variable of the respondents. The value of the calculated P is less than the value of the P-table.

This finding can be explained by the fact that workers of all ages live in the same organizational climate, both in decision-making and in the nature of work, and are affected by all of them.

Table 14: Source of variance, sum of squares, degrees of freedom, mean squares, P value, and significance level

Field	Source	Total Squares	Degrees of Freedom	Average Squares	P Value	Sig.
The extent of participation of	Between Groups	3.214	2	1.607	3.970	0.021

This hypothesis is divided into several sub-hypotheses as follows:

H02-1: There are statistically significant differences between the extent of participation of decision makers and the nature of work prevailing in universities according to the gender variable.

To determine the validity of this hypothesis, the researchers used the T-test as shown in the following table:

Differences between males and females in the nature of work can be explained by the fact that the majority of female jobs are minimal in the organizational structure such as secretarial functions.

H02-2: There are statistically significant differences between the extent of participation of decision makers and the nature of work prevailing in universities according to the age variable.

To determine the validity of this hypothesis, one way anova was used as shown in the following table:

H02-3: There are statistically significant differences between the extent of participation of decision makers and the nature of work prevailing in universities according to the variable of scientific qualification.

To determine the validity of this hypothesis, one way anova was used as shown in the following table:

Field	Source	Total Squares	Degrees of Freedom	Average Squares	P Value	Sig.
	Within Groups	72.468	179	0.405		
	Total	75.682	181			
	Between Groups	3.617	2	1.809		
the Nature of Work	Within Groups	65.834	179	0.368	4.917	0.008
	Total	69.451	181			

It is clear from the previous table that there are statistically significant differences in the extent of participation of decision-makers and the nature of work according to their scientific qualifications. The value of P is less than the value of the P-table. This result can be explained by the fact that workers of various scientific qualifications aspire to their

participation in the decision-making process and to improve the nature of their work.

To find out the direction of the differences, the Scheffe Test was used in the following tables:

Table 15: Results of the Scheffe Test to identify the direction of differences and their significance in the field of participation of decision-making workers due to the variable of scientific qualification

Qualification	Diploma	BA	Postgraduate
Diploma	-		
BA	0.160210-	-	
Postgraduate	*0.398068-	0.237858-	-

* Significant at (0.05)

It is clear from the previous table that there are statistically significant differences at the level of (0.05) due to the variable of scientific qualification in the extent of participation of decision-makers among those with postgraduate qualifications with diplomas for those with a diploma qualification. With diploma holders in favor of diploma holders. This finding can be explained by the fact that those with postgraduate qualifications are often

dissatisfied with their degree of decision-making as a result of the university's failure to properly assess them and grant those jobs commensurate with their qualifications, there is also a decrease in the minimum educational qualifications. We also note from the table that there are no statistically significant differences between the other qualifications.

Table 16: Results of the Scheffe Test to determine the direction and significance of differences in the nature of work due to the variable of scientific qualification

Qualification	Diploma	BA	Postgraduate
Diploma	-		
BA	0.244200-	-	
Postgraduate	*0.396294-	0.152094-	-

* Significant at (0.05)

It is clear from the previous table that there are statistically significant differences at the level of (0.05) attributed to the variable of the scientific qualification in the "nature of work" among the holders of the qualifications of postgraduate studies with diploma holders in favor of holders of a diploma qualification, and the absence of differences between those with postgraduate qualifications with a bachelor's degree in favor of holders of bachelor's qualifications. The researchers explain this finding that graduates with postgraduate qualifications are often dissatisfied with their jobs and therefore the nature of work as a result of not being given

jobs commensurate with their qualifications; furthermore, that there are no statistically significant differences between diploma holders and holders of bachelor's degrees.

H02-4: There are statistically significant differences between the extent of participation of decision makers and the nature of work prevailing in universities according to the variable years of service.

To determine the validity of this hypothesis, one way anova was used as shown in the following table:

Table 17: Source of variance, sum of squares, degrees of freedom, mean squares, P value and significance level due to variable years of service

Field	Source	Total Squares	Degrees of Freedom	Average Squares	P Value	Sig.
The extent of participation of	Between Groups	4.829	3	1.610	4.044	0.008

Field	Source	Total Squares	Degrees of Freedom	Average Squares	P Value	Sig.
	Within Groups	70.853	178	0.398		
	Total	75.682	181			
the Nature of Work	Between Groups	3.931	3	1.310	3.560	0.015
	Within Groups	65.520	178	0.368		
	Total	69.451	181			

The above table shows that the value of "P" calculated above the value of "P" table, and therefore there are differences of statistical significance in all areas and this proves the validity of the hypothesis.

To find out the direction of the differences, the Scheffe Test was used in the following tables:

Table 18: The results of the Scheffe Test to identify the direction and significance of differences in the extent of participation of decision makers due to the variable years of service

Years of service	Less than 5 years	5-7 years	8-10 years	More than 10 years
Less than 5 years	-			
5-7 years	*0.409135	-		
8-10 years	0.223533	0.185602-	-	
More than 10 years	0.008380	*0.400755-	0.215153-	-

* Significant at (0.05)

It is clear from the previous table that there are statistically significant differences at the level of (0.05) due to the variable of years of service in the extent of participation of decision-making workers between the years of service (5-7 years) and those with years of service (less than 5 years) and (more than 10 years) in favor of (5-7 years). The researchers explain this finding that the owners of the years of service

(5-7) are in the stage of career growth and are often satisfied with the nature of their work which is greater than other categories that seek to improve the nature of their work, and we note from the table that there are no statistically significant differences between the categories of other years of service.

Table 19: Results of the Scheffe Test to identify the direction and significance of differences in the nature of work due to the variable years of service

Years of service	Less than 5 years	5-7 years	8-10 years	More than 10 years
Less than 5 years	-			
5-7 years	0.191382	-		
8-10 years	0.104160	0.087222-	-	
More than 10 years	0.173111-	*0.364493-	0.277271-	-

* Significant at (0.05)

It is clear from the previous table that there are statistically significant differences at the level of (0.05) due to the variable of years of service in the fifth field "nature of work" between the owners of the service years (5-7 years) and the years of service (more than 10 years) in favor of (5-7 years). The researchers explain this result that the owners of the years of service (5-7), are in the stage of career development and are often satisfied with the nature of their work, and this is more so in the owners of other years of service and who seek to improve the nature of their work, and we note from

the table that there are no statistically significant differences between the categories of other years of service.

H02-5: There are statistically significant differences between the extent of participation of decision makers and the nature of work prevailing in universities according to the level of employment.

To determine the validity of this hypothesis, one way anova was used as shown in the following table:

Table 20: Source of variance, sum of squares, degrees of freedom, mean squares, P value, and significance level

Field	Source	Total Squares	Degrees of Freedom	Average Squares	P Value	Sig.
The extent of participation of	Between Groups	0.432	2	0.216	0.514	0.599

Field	Source	Total Squares	Degrees of Freedom	Average Squares	P Value	Sig.
	Within Groups	75.249	179	0.420		
	Total	75.682	181			
	Between Groups	0.214	2	0.107		
the Nature of Work	Within Groups	69.237	179	0.387	0.276	0.759
	Total	69.451	181			
	Between Groups	0.214	2	0.107		

It is clear from the previous table that the calculated P value is less than the P value of the table, meaning that there are no statistically significant differences in all fields of the scale according to the functional level variable, which proves the hypothesis is incorrect.

H02-6: There are statistically significant differences between the extent of participation of decision makers and the nature

Table 21: Source of variance, sum of squares, degrees of freedom, mean squares, value of "P", and level of significance attributed to the variable of the workplace

Field	Source	Total Squares	Degrees of Freedom	Average Squares	P Value	Sig.
The extent of participation of decision makers	Between Groups	2.572	3	0.857	2.087	0.104
	Within Groups	73.110	178	0.411		
	Total	75.682	181			
the Nature of Work	Between Groups	0.387	3	0.129	0.333	0.802
	Within Groups	69.064	178	0.388		
	Total	69.451	181			

The above table shows that the calculated "P" value is less than the "P" value of the table, meaning that there are no statistically significant differences in all fields, which proves the hypothesis is incorrect.

This finding can be explained by the fact that the working environment at the university is rather intertwined and convergent, which makes the workers' perception of the extent to which decision makers and the nature of work are similar.

Table 22: Standard Meanings, Deviations, and Value of the Fields of the Participation Scale of Administrative Personnel in Decision-Making and Their Relationship to the Nature of Work according to the University Variable

Field	The University	The Number	Mean	Standard Deviation	"T" Value	Level of Sig.
The extent of participation of decision makers	Islamic University	111	3.4863	0.53810	2.598	0.010
	Al-Azhar University	71	3.2349	0.76620		
the Nature of Work	Islamic University	111	3.8382	0.53106	2.489	0.014
	Al-Azhar University	71	3.6072	.718310		

The above table shows that the calculated "T" value is greater than the "T" table value. Therefore, there are statistically significant differences in all fields of the university variable. This proves the validity of the hypothesis. The differences were to the Islamic university. The Islamic University is the oldest and most stable university in the world, a public university. Al-Azhar University, which is exposed to financial crises from time to time, derives mainly from the fees paid by students for funding. Which affects their performance and the prevailing organizational climate.

of work prevailing in universities according to the variable of the workplace.

To determine the validity of this hypothesis, one way anova was used as shown in the following table:

H03: There are differences related statistically between the extent of participation of decision makers and the nature of work prevailing in universities depending on the university in which they work.

To determine the validity of this hypothesis, one way anova was used as shown in the following table:

13. RESULTS

- The results showed that there is a medium degree of participation of decision-making staff in the Palestinian universities in the Gaza Strip from the point of view of the administrative staff, which reached 67.76%.
- The results showed that there was a high level of satisfaction with the nature of work, with a percentage (74.96%).

- The results showed that there is a positive correlation between the participation of decision makers and the prevailing nature of work.
- The results showed that there were differences between the sample according to the gender variable in their perception of the participation of decision makers and the nature of work. In favor of female participation in decision-making and in favor of males in the nature of work.
- The results indicate that there are no differences in the perception of employees to participate in decision-making and the nature of work according to the variable age.
- The results showed that there are statistically significant differences in the perception of participation of decision makers and the nature of work according to the variable of scientific qualification.
- The results showed that the differences in the participation of decision makers and the nature of work according to the scientific qualification were in favor of the diploma holders compared to other practical qualifications.
- The results indicate that there are no differences in the perception of employees to participate in decision-making and the nature of work according to the variable years of service for the years of service (5-7 years)
- The results indicate that there are no differences in the perception of employees to participate in decision-making and the nature of work according to the variable level of the job (manager, head of department, administrative officer).
- The results indicate that there are no differences in the perception of employees to participate in decision-making and the nature of work according to the variable of the workplace.
- The results indicate that there are differences in the perception of employees to participate in decision-making and the nature of work according to the university working for the Islamic University.

14. RECOMMENDATIONS

- The interest of the departments of Palestinian universities in the Gaza Strip should be increased with the participation of decision-makers by delegating authority and using the democratic approach to leadership.
- Continuing administration of the universities of interest and continuous improvement of the nature of the work of its employees.
- To enhance the periodic evaluation of job performance and to inform employees and express their opinion.
- Solve employee problems and give them the opportunity to contribute to solving their own problems.

- Use the staff rotation method periodically.

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